

sence of moisture. The azo compounds of COOHBAN are all deep red coloured and are thermally stable. When heated, they decompose at a temperature much higher than the melting point of the ligand and also of the alkali metal salts. The colour, melting or decomposition temperatures and analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The presence of COOH and OH groups in the *o*- and *o'*-position to the azo group suggested the possibility of strong intra-molecular hydrogen bonding in ligand COOHBAN.

The -OH stretching frequency at 3050 cm⁻¹ (br) of the ligand is missing in the adducts. However, in KSCN adduct, the band appears at higher frequency (3450 cm⁻¹). Broad band with two sub-maxima at 2600 and 2450 cm⁻¹ are obtained in the adducts, whereas the ligand only shows one band at 2450 cm⁻¹ with lower intensity due to stronger hydrogen bonding.

The asymmetric stretch of the C=O group shows up at 1710 cm⁻¹ in the ligand. In the alkali metal adducts, it appears between 1620-1630 cm⁻¹, and is suggestive² of coordination of C=O group to the alkali metals.

The -N=N- frequency in the ligand shows up at 1580 cm⁻¹. In the alkali metal adducts, this appears between 1560-1570 cm⁻¹.

From the infrared spectra of the ligand and adducts, it may be suggested that the attachment is through -OH, C=O, and -N=N- groups of the ligand COOHBAN.

References

1. "Organic Syntheses, Coll. Volume", John Wiley and Sons, Inc, 2nd Edn., p. 581.
2. W. L. DRIJSSSEN, W. L. GROENEVELD and F. W. VANDERWEY, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1970, 89, 353.

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) with Iminodiacetic Acid as Primary Ligand and Amino Acids as Secondary Ligand

J. D. JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 17 March 1983, accepted 28 November 1983

BHATTACHARYA and co-workers have investigated^{1,2} the mixed ligand system (MAL) involving bivalent metal ions like Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and histidine, iminodiacetic acid or nitrilotriacetic acid as primary ligand and polyhydroxy phenols or amino acids as secondary ligand. Various mixed ligand complexes with iminodiacetic acid (IMDA)³ as the primary ligand have been studied. In the present investigation, attempts have been made to study the formation constants of the title systems in

presence of equivalent and excess amount of secondary ligand L, using modified form of Irving-Rossotti⁴ titration technique.

IMDA is known to form 1:1 complex with Zn(II) or Cd(II) at pH ~6 and ~6.5, respectively and the complex is stable at higher pH, where the combination of secondary ligand starts. The reaction can be shown as follows:

$$K_{MAL}^{MA} = \frac{[MAL]}{[MA][L]}$$

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. quality. Zn(II) and Cd(II) perchlorates were prepared from their respective carbonates and the metal content were determined and checked. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of all the solutions.

The experimental set up and methods of calculations described by Bhattacharya and co-workers¹ were employed. The measurements were carried out at 30°.

The nature of the potentiometric titration curves was interpreted by the method adopted in earlier publications. In the secondary ligand two equivalent extra acid was added to account for the extra hydrogen ions liberated due to the combination of primary ligand, IMDA. $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated using the same equation as in earlier cases⁵. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{MA} were obtained by using the method of averages⁶. The values are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The order of the formation constants of the ternary complexes is the same as that for the binary complexes^{7,8}. However, the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} are significantly lower than the values of the first formation constant K_{ML}^M of the binary complexes and are slightly lower than the second formation constant $K_{ML_2}^M$ of the binary complexes. The same order is observed in the case of excess amount of the secondary ligand L.

The results can be explained by considering that the electrostatic repulsion between the primary ligand iminodiacetic acid and the secondary ligand amino acid is more. Iminodiacetic acid bears two negative charges and hence the coordinating tendency of the secondary ligand L to combine with [M(IMDA)] decreases significantly. Therefore, the mixed ligand formation constant values are significantly lower than K_{ML}^M and slightly lower than $K_{ML_2}^M$. The $\log K_{ML}^M - \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ value is higher than unity in case of Zn(II) and lower in case of Cd(II). This is due to the smaller size of Zn(II) and bigger size of Cd(II), respectively. Besides the

TABLE I—MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF Zn(II) AND Cd(II) AT 30° (Ionic strength=0.2 M)

Ligand (L)	$\log K_{Zn,L}^{Zn^*}$	$\log K_{Zn,A,L}^{Zn,A}$ (1 : 1 : 1)	$\Delta \dagger$	$\log K_{Cd,L}^{Cd^*}$	$\log K_{Cd,A,L}^{Cd,A}$ (1 : 1 : 1)	$\Delta \dagger$
Glycine	5.22	4.11	1.11	4.22	3.55	0.67
α -Alanine	5.17	3.84	1.33	4.27	3.40	0.87
Leucine	4.74	3.54	1.21	3.92	3.00	0.92
Iso-Leucine	4.88	3.59	1.30	3.94	3.00	0.94
Valine	4.74	3.50	1.24	3.91	3.02	0.89
Serine	5.06	4.00	1.06	3.95	3.05	0.90
Threonine	5.16	4.08	1.08	4.02	3.25	0.77
Methionine	4.69	3.59	1.10	4.04	3.20	0.84

$$\dagger \Delta = \log K_{ML}^M - \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$$

* Values taken from literature for comparison.

$$\text{Deviation in } \log K_{MAL}^{MA} \pm 0.05$$

charge repulsion, other factors may also affect the mixed ligand formation constant.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Professor P. K. Bhattacharya, M. S. University, Baroda for valuable guidance.

References

- I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 742.
- M. V. CHIDAMBARAM, and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1975, 75, 123.
- B. E. LEACH and R. J. ANGELICI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 907.
- H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
- I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 469.
- S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 73.
- M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 881.
- M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 941.

Aromatic and N-Substitution Reactions Involving Nickel and Copper Complexes of Schiff Base Derivatives of 2-Hydroxy Acetophenone

B. T. THAKER

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 27 October 1980, revised 8 November 1982, accepted 28 April 1983

BROMINATION occurs at the 5- or 3- and 5-positions of the ligand in a range of salicylaldiminato metal complexes¹⁻⁴. The electron density at 3 and 5 carbon of the benzene ring of the ligand is an

important factor in the success or failure of electrophilic or free radical substitutions. This electron density is dependent on the type of metal ion as well as the nature of other substituents present in the complex⁵.

No comprehensive investigation of the reactions involving bidentate Schiff base ligand complexes derived from 2-hydroxy-acetophenone has been reported. An attempt was, therefore, made to study the orientation effect by carrying out the bromination reactions on *bis*-(bidentate Schiff base)-complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II). N-Substitution reactions were carried out on brominated copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes by amine exchange. The structure of the resulting Schiff base complexes has been discussed and the mechanism of the bromination reaction has been suggested.

An investigation of bromination and amine exchange reactions involving the complex (I) is reported here.

Experimental

Bis[1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneamine or its methyl derivatives]Cu(II) or Ni(II) were prepared as reported earlier⁶. *Bis*[1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneoxime or its methyl derivatives]Cu(II) or Ni(II) were prepared by amine exchange method⁷. N-Bromo succinimide (Sisco), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (S.M.), sodium acetate (Pfizer) and bromine solution were used. Ethanol and chloroform were of analytical grade.